

Montpelier Wetland Project, Williams County

Since construction in 2023, the capacity of soils to sorb phosphate remained similar from year to year at the Montpelier Wetland Project, indicating a potential for soil nutrient retention. The impact of the Project's phosphorus filter is being evaluated by affiliate researchers, who also collect water samples and estimated nutrient filtration at this Project¹. Though the dry conditions throughout 2024 likely limited its overall efficacy, the Project filtered 2.8 lbs phosphorus per acre. Its runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field and removal as a nutrient source also prevents approximately 0.3 lbs phosphorus export per acre each year.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is passively managed. The Project has approximately 8.5 acres of restored wetland and consists of a southern wetland with a flow-through wetland system, and a northern wetland with a series of small depressional wetlands. The southern wetland receives water through a tile outlet on the eastern side and outlets into an underground phosphorus filter which outflows into a ditch, while the northern wetland receives water from surface runoff. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a storm event in which the eastern tile delivers water to the flow-through wetland system.

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- No considerations to report at this time. Affiliate researchers are analyzing surface water for nutrient concentration. The Monitoring Program will support data interpretation where possible. The results of evaluation of the function of the phosphorus filter in this Project will help to indicate the potential benefit of this type of facility for enhancing wetland performance, especially as the southwest wetland is receiving water from a legacy-phosphorus field which is expected to deliver high phosphorus concentration.

¹ Stoltzfus, Brooker, and Martin, Unpublished Results, 2025

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.